

THE IMPORTANCE OF MEDICINAL PLANTS IN PROPER
NUTRITION AND INCREASED IMMUNITY

Khairullayeva M.Sh., PhD Nasriddinova M.R.

Karshi State University

E-mail: m.nasriddinova@mail.ru

Raising healthy, educated, broad-minded and intellectually mature youth is one of the policy priorities of our state. We all know that normal growth and health of the body depends on proper nutrition. Currently, an increase in the number of products with GMOs and the consumption of semi-finished products negatively affects the immune system. Decreased immunity in children affects their mental activity. This is why we should use medicinal plants to strengthen our immunity and meet our daily needs. When immunity decreases, a number of diseases occur, primarily anemia, liver and stomach diseases. Along with proper nutrition, medicinal plants are also important for maintaining health and boosting immunity.

Natural medicinal herbs not only make a great contribution to the recovery of the patient, to the treatment of a certain disease, but also serve to prevent the occurrence and prevention of a certain disease. Natural plants are valuable because they contain large amounts of vitamins and other biologically active substances. Vitamins, including vitamin C, take part in the biosynthesis of protein in the body and strengthening the immune system; B vitamins speed up metabolism; Vitamin E increases muscle mass, develops strength and agility; vitamin A is important for improving vision, controlling growth and development; vitamin D strengthens bone tissue

Capsella bursa pastoris, *Spinacia turkestanica*, *Taraxasum officinalis*, *Melissa officinalis*, *Mentha asiatica* - plants rich in vitamins from common medicinal plants of the flora of our republic [1].

Capsella bursa pastoris (maxillary), which begins growing in early spring and is also known in the local language as achambiti, is included in the group of vitamin plants, as it contains a lot of ascorbic acid. Our plants such as *Spinacia turkestanica* (spinach), *Taraxasum officinalis* (parsley), *Mentha asiatica* (mint) are especially rich in vitamins and grow in abundance around fields, fields, roadsides and houses [2].

From time immemorial, dishes rich in medicinal substances (blue somsa, blue dumplings, salads), prepared by our people in early spring, give energy to the body.

Based on this, it would not be superfluous to include tinctures or decoctions in your daily diet. Drinking tea with lemon and mint instead of liquid drinks during meals has a very good effect on the immune system and the central nervous system. Herbal teas, tinctures or decoctions of medicinal species refresh the body, improve digestion and relieve various pains in the body.

In addition, naturally prepared herbal teas can be used at any time of the year if they are collected from the above-ground parts of the selected species and dried.

From the information provided, it is clear that medicinal plants play an important role in proper nutrition and serve to ensure human health and longevity. Therefore, the protection of medicinal plants, prevention of depletion of natural reserves, their rational use and conservation is an important task for every person.

References

1. Kholmatov Kh.Kh., Kasimov A.I. Medicinal plants. Tashkent, NMB "Ibn Sino", 1994. – P. 365.
2. Khodzhimatov K.Kh., Yoldoshev K.Yu., Shogulumov U.Sh., Khodzhimatov O.Q. Medicinal herbs - a cure for pain. Tashkent, 1995. – P. 142.